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Summary

This deliverable presents the methodology developed for mapping the diversity of energy citizenship in Europe, arrived at through a collaborative process with the involvement of all project partners. The development of the methodology, and its outcome, the present deliverable, can be viewed as the first step in the operationalisation of the conceptual framework and typology of energy citizenship as developed in the project.

Participants brainstorm at a carbon club event

Moving house using cargobikes

Members of a neighbourhood community plant trees after having calculated their carbon footprints

Fridays for Future climate protesters

Members of a community learn to insulate their windows using DIY methods

Introducing visitors to renewable energy technology at an 'open door day' event

Figure 1: Some of the manifestations of energy citizenship in Hungary

Introduction

This deliverable presents the methodology developed for pursuing the overall project aim of identifying the diversity of types and empirical manifestations of energy citizenship. At the same time, it is the third step in the process of interaction between the theory and practice of energy citizenship, following the development of the conceptual framework and typology.

The main research questions the project team intends to answer with the methodology presented here are the following:

- Which forms of energy citizenship (henceforth referred to as ENCI) can be found in Europe today? How can we account for their diversity?
- Can we find the same forms in different regions/countries of Europe?
- In what contexts do different forms of ENCI emerge and develop?

Below we first present the objectives of the work package (WP3) concerned with the mapping of ENCI followed by the definition of ENCI and what constitutes a case of ENCI, and finally the details of the methodology development process and the methodology itself.

1. Objectives of WP3 and D3.1

The overall objectives of WP3 are to

- review at least 500 cases of energy citizenship in Europe, and through this review contribute to the operationalisation of the conceptual framework and typology developed earlier in the project, namely in WP2;
- guided by the conceptual framework and the typology select cc. 40 cases from the mapping (review) of energy citizenship for in-depth analysis in WP3 as well as for further study mainly in WP4 (*role of intermediaries, ICT, transactions, and institutional arrangements and governance*), but also in WP5 (*contextual conditions of energy citizenship*) and WP6 (*policies for energy citizenship*);
- develop and share with various stakeholders a case study collection methodology (both for the mapping of energy citizenship (ENCI) and in-depth analysis of ENCI cases) with various stakeholders;
- complete the case-by-case as well as meta-analysis of the cc. 40 in-depth ENCI cases; and
- develop an empowerment energy citizenship toolkit.

The specific objective of the current deliverable (D3.1) is to present the methodology used for reviewing / mapping ENCI. The methodology will

- enable the mapping and selection of cases for the catalogue of 500+ cases of energy citizenship in Europe;
- contribute to the operationalisation of the conceptual framework and typology developed in WP2;
- support the collection of both quantitative and qualitative data about the context of energy citizenship, e.g. what inspires its conception and establishment, which objectives they wish to achieve, which actors are involved and contribute to its development, how they are funded, what kind of changes they go through, etc.; and
- contribute to the selection of cases for detailed case study data collection.

Based on these objectives, and as shown in Figure 2, the cases data collection in WP3 is an integral and central task in the EnergyPROSPECTS project as it is linked to theory development in WP2, and then contributes to all subsequent work to be carried out in various work packages.

Figure 2: The integration of WP3 data collection tasks in the EnergyPROSPECTS project

Task 3.1 and deliverable D3.1 will serve as the basis for all subsequent work in WP3 as well, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The flow of activities and tasks in WP3

As can be seen in Figures 2 and 3, there are tasks related to typology development both in WP2 and WP3. This is part of an iterative typology development process (Figure 4), and merits some explanation:

- in WP2 a conceptual typology (see in [D2.2](#), Debourdeau et al., 2021) has been developed based mainly on the conceptual framework ([D2.1](#), Pel et al., 2021) and early interaction with WP3 during the development of the methodology presented here (see Figure 6). This typology has informed the definition of what is considered a 'case' in the project as well as subsequent methodology development and cases collection in WP3;
- the conceptual typology is then validated and further refined through the empirical work undertaken in WP3, i.e. through the case collection and analysis work;

Figure 4: Iterative typology development process informed by theory and practice

- finally, as part of Task 3.3, in addition to the refinement of the conceptual typology originally developed in WP2, further typologies *may be* developed depending on the results of the case analysis. For example, based on some of the distinctions identified and discussed in [D2.1](#) (Pel et al., 2021) and/or to illustrate and highlight specific tendencies or forms of ENCI in more detail (e.g. a typology may be developed based on the climate justice-ecological (or carbon) limits principles, i.e. to see how energy citizenship contributes to the overall sustainable energy objectives of climate / energy justice on the one hand, and to staying within our carbon budget and implementing 1.5° lifestyles on the other). These aspects, although identified in the conceptual framework deliverable, [D2.1](#) (Pel et al., 2021), were not discussed in detail there. However, through specific methodology development they could be explored in more detail through the empirical manifestations of energy citizenship identified as a result of the mapping activity. Furthermore, as the manifest/latent distinctions did clarify in [D2.1](#) (see Figure 5) that certain kinds of ENCI are likely to contribute to these sustainability goals more than others.

Figure 5: ENCI conceptual framework: manifest/latent forms along seven key distinctions (Pel et al., 2021:61)

1.1. The process of developing D3.1 or the ENCI mapping methodology

As already indicated above in Figure 4, the level of collaboration between WP2 and WP3 was intended to be high in order to achieve a shared understanding of the energy citizenship concept and to operationalise it in practice. As part of this collaborative process (shown in Figure 6), several online workshops were held. Some of these involved the core WP2 and WP3 teams, some the whole consortium. Commenting on the various drafts of D3.1 was carried out in a similar fashion: certain drafts were only reviewed by the core Task 3.1 team including WP2 and WP4 leaders, and others by the whole consortium in order to ensure that the research objectives and data needs of all WPs can be best fulfilled by the ENCI mapping methodology. The various deliverable drafts were informed by discussion at the workshops as well as the conceptual framework (D2.1) and typology (D2.2) throughout the process.

Figure 6: The collaborative process of developing D3.1, or the ENCI mapping methodology

2. Inputs to the methodology and the definition of energy citizenship

As indicated above, the methodology development process and resulting data collection methodology needed to be informed by various project tasks as well as the limits set by the resources available in EnergyPROSPECTS:

- First of all, the conceptual framework for energy citizenship (Pel et al., 2021), contributed the definition of ENCI, helping to draw the boundaries of the case collection as well as define what type of cases to collect, including ideal types as defined in Debourdeau et al. (2021), and potentially other latent and manifest cases of ENCI;
- Secondly, the conceptual typology of energy citizenship (Debourdeau et al., 2021) has guided the case collection process in terms of what kind of cases could constitute ideal types and what type of data is needed to operationalise and, if needed, refine the typology;
- Thirdly, the data and information needs of WP4, WP5 and WP6 helped define the type of data the consortium would be collecting about the cases of ENCI (see more about this in Chapter 4);
- Finally, the methodology development process was guided by the overall objectives of the project that pertain to identify and analyse the diversity of forms and contexts of ENCI in Europe, and to explore in what ways they contribute to the sustainable energy transition.

2.1. Defining ENCI and what a case is

For the definition of energy citizenship we turn to the conceptual framework presented in [D2.1](#):

Energy citizenship refers to forms of civic involvement that pertain to the development of a more sustainable and democratic energy system. Beyond its manifest forms, ENCI also comprises various latent forms: it is an ideal that can be lived up to and realised to varying degrees, according to different framework conditions and states of empowerment.’ (Pel et al., 2021:64 and see Figure 5 above)

Building on this definition of energy citizenship, a case of ENCI in the EnergyPROSPECTS project

1. is a constellation of actors (in a context) and how it
 - ✓ enables/supports citizens to become active private and/or public energy citizens;
 - ✓ acts as a collective energy citizen by contributing to change of the energy system

or

2. includes individual energy citizens and how they realize their potential in a private, public or organisational setting.

As indicated by these definitions, and underlined by the agency dimension of the conceptual typology presented in Debourdeau et al. (2021), a case can be centred around an individual, or realised in a multitude of collective forms. During the mapping of the ENCI landscape focus will be placed on collecting both types of cases (*see more details in section 3.1 below on the sampling strategy*).

Furthermore, as there is a huge variety of cases and initiatives available that would fit these definitions, and mapping them all would go beyond the scope and resources of the current project, there was need to further define what is considered a case within the research focus of the EnergyPROSPECTS projects. Thus, the consortium decided at team workshops (Figure 6) that the ENCI mapping activity will cover cases that:

- are **based in European countries** (including EU, EEA and accession countries);
- are **currently active or were concluded no sooner than 2015** when the Energy Union Strategy was published.
This is because the focus in this research is not so much on the historical forms of ENCI, but rather its current forms and manifestations, and the differences between them depending on the political, socio-economic, etc. characteristics of their context;
- are **focused on direct energy production and/or consumption** (e.g. in households, organizations, etc.), **mobility** (with a direct connection to energy issues), or have a **more holistic overall focus on sustainable and just energy**. This means that in EnergyPROSPECTS a decision was made not to study initiatives that focus solely on nutrition, for example. However, if nutrition is part of an overall strategy for energy use or carbon footprint reduction, that also focuses on direct energy use, mobility, etc., then the case can be included (*see more details and examples in section 3.1 below on the sampling strategy*).

As both Pel et al. (2021) and Debourdeau et al. (2021) indicate, we also recognise that even within the limitations set for ENCI mapping "enabling" and "supporting" citizens to become active private and/or public energy citizens can take many different forms. Similarly, energy citizenship itself can have many different forms. Furthermore, many cases in reality enable or support several different forms of energy citizenship in parallel, often less as well as more active forms within the same case (e.g. citizens voluntarily organising carbon reduction groups as a more active form of citizenship, and citizens participating in these groups as a less active form).

As a result it is expected that a very diverse collection of ENCI cases will emerge as an output of the mapping process. Indeed, it is important to note that although the term *energy citizenship* is often associated with energy communities or community energy projects, the objective in the EnergyPROSPECTS project is to uncover other forms of

energy citizenship as well, including both individual and collective forms of citizenship. It appears that as the climate emergency has been entering the sphere of mainstream societal discussion, a variety of forms of related citizenship have been emerging, for example as a result of people and communities searching for ways to assume responsibility and realize their potentials as energy (and climate) citizens in various ways in different contexts. Some examples of these are given in section 3.1 below related to the discussion of the EnergyPROSPECTS sampling strategy, but a more complete picture will emerge and will be provided both through a public online database and academic publications once the mapping process is concluded.

3. Overview of the stages and steps of the data collection process

There are two main stages of data collection in WP3 (Table 1). First, during stage 1 of the process, a wider scale mapping and review of energy citizenship cases will take place, resulting in at least 500 cases, collected in project partner countries, as well as in other EU, EEA and accession countries. During this stage the objective is to map the diversity of the forms of ENCI in Europe, informed by the conceptual framework (Pel et al., 2021) and typology (Debourdeau et al., 2021) developed in WP2 on the one hand, and contributing to their operationalisation and development on the other. Furthermore, the aim of the cases review and data collection process is also to contribute to subsequent work in the EnergyPROSPECTS project.

Stages	Main objective of data collection	Target no. of cases	Level of data collection	Methodology development	Published in
1	Review and mapping of energy citizenship cases	500+	shallow / light	Task 3.1, including piloting	D3.1 (GDI)
2	In-depth, detailed study of energy citizenship cases	cc. 40	deep	Task 3.4, including piloting	D3.3 (ULB)

Table 1: Stages of data collection and analysis in WP3 of the EnergyPROSPECTS project

In stage 2 of the data collection process cc. 40 cases will be selected for in-depth analysis from the 500+ cases collected in stage 1. Furthermore, this second stage of the data collection process will provide more detailed data for work that will be carried out in WP3 as well as in WP4, WP5 and WP6.

The two stages of data collection and how they are linked to other parts of the project are shown in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7: The two stages of data collection in WP3 and their interaction with other WPs

3.1.Challenges for ENCI mapping: sampling strategy

During Stage 1 of the data collection process, i.e. the mapping of ENCI, the project team will need to find a balance between geographical diversity of cases as well as diversity in forms of ENCI and typological diversity.

Furthermore, in countries well known by the team, or in countries where ENCI is widely practiced, a larger number of cases may be identified in comparison to countries where ENCI is not (yet) widely practiced, or where language skills present a barrier for the team. For this reason, a **sampling strategy was developed** (Table 4) and discussed at the various online methodology development workshops (Figure 6) to refine it with the aim of using it to guide the ENCI mapping process.

The sampling strategy has five different layers:

- The first layer of the strategy is about ensuring that an appropriate level of **geographical diversity is achieved, and that ENCI in all European countries** - including EU countries, EEA countries as well as EU accession countries - is considered.

ENCI in various countries will be mapped by different project partners based on available language skills and existing contacts to local organisations, including

cooperation in previous relevant projects. Annex I includes the division of countries between project partners.

- The second layer of the strategy concerns the **main focus of the ENCI cases**. Based on the original research plans as summarised in the Grant Agreement and further clarification obtained during workshop discussions, the project team agreed to map ENCI cases that focus on
 1. direct energy consumption and/or production;
 2. mobility; and
 3. holistic cases that nevertheless maintain a direct focus on either direct energy consumption and/or production or mobility (e.g. cases focusing on carbon footprint reduction, cases adopting a lifestyle change approach, or cases focusing on the sustainable energy transition/climate neutrality of a town/region through developing plans/public involvement and consultation, etc.)

Examples of all three types are provided in Table 2 below, and the objective of mapping is to find ENCI case examples for all three types of focus if available.

Main focus	ENCI type examples
Direct energy consumption and/or production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renovation • Active/passive/autonomous houses • Behaviour/practice change based • Metering, smart metering • Equipment replacement for more energy efficient • Equipment sharing • Renewable energy • Prosumer oriented • etc.
Mobility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carfree living, carfree districts • Cycling related cases • Travel less • No-flight initiatives • Sharing cars • Walk (or cycle) to school initiatives (e.g. walking bus) • 15/20-minute cities • etc.
Holistic cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon footprint reduction based cases • Communities, e.g. eco villages • Sufficiency oriented cases • Movements: Fridays for Future, Extinction rebellion • Transition towns • Low-carbon settlements/regions • Citizen assemblies • etc.

Table 2: Examples of ENCI cases related to their main focus

- The third layer of the strategy is aimed at ensuring that both **individual and collective cases of ENCI** are mapped.

As individual cases are perhaps less usual and are thus more difficult to find, Table 3 provides some examples. Annex III includes further examples and also tips for identifying such cases.

Examples of individual ENCI cases
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientists becoming activists • Individuals caring very much about low-footprint living and exemplifying and communicating about it • Certain influencers • People single-handedly leading change (in their organisation, their political constituency or in society more broadly), e.g. managers, majors, and activists • Individuals taking legal action against their municipality/country/the EU because of insufficient level of climate planning and action

Table 3: Examples of individual ENCI cases

- The fourth layer of the sampling strategy is intended to ensure that a **diversity in terms of the types of ENCI as summarised by the conceptual typology (D2.2)** are searched for and mapped, and uses the typology as guidance for identifying and selecting cases.

Figure 8 provides a summary of the conceptual typology and the ideal types denoted by it.

AGENCY		INDIVIDUAL			COLLECTIVE	
OUTCOME ORIENTATION	PRIVATE (HOUSEHOLD)	ORGANISATIONALLY EMBEDDED (E.G., WORKPLACE)	PUBLIC	CITIZEN-BASED AND HYBRID	SOCIAL MOVEMENTS	
REFORMATIVE 	1. DO THEIR BIT (in the household) Complying with the green energy transition	3. DO THEIR BIT (within organisations) Energy citizenship within organisations	5. MAKE THEIR VOICE HEARD Participating in societal energy discussions	7. DO THEIR SHARE Joining green energy projects	9. DO THE JOB Facilitating the energy transition through alignment activities	
TRANSFORMATIVE 	2. DO THEIR OWN (in the household) The change-making energy citizen	4. DO IT THEIR WAY (within organisations) The energy-related change maker in organisations	6. MAKE THEIR VOTE COUNT Mobilising votes for energy transition	8. GO AHEAD Building, expanding and linking citizen-based organisational forms	10. MAKE THEIR CLAIM Protesting against the current energy system	

Figure 8: The conceptual typology developed for the EnergyPROSPECTS project (Debourdeau et al., 2021)

- Finally, the last layer of the sampling strategy is a reminder that diversity should also be aimed for in terms of searching for and mapping cases that focus on
 - ✓ gendered aspects of the energy and/or climate transition,
 - ✓ energy poverty,
 - ✓ disadvantaged groups,
 - ✓ urban and rural areas,
 - ✓ as well as cases that adopt a behaviour or practice change approach and also a more technology-based approach.

Layer	Focus	Proposed numbers / division of cases
1. geography	Diversity in where the cases are based in terms of groups of countries <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Cases need to be collected in 3 main country groups: EU countries / EEA / accession countries. ➤ There is no need to collect an equal number of cases in each country, as this may not be achievable. ➤ In terms of EU countries, we can expect a certain level of bias (i.e. more cases) towards the countries where the EP partners are based. But since this covers different European regions, this is acceptable. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ cc. 400-450 in EU -- 27 countries ➤ cc.40-50 in EEA -- 4 countries, incl. UK ➤ cc. 40-50 in accession - 5 countries
2. main focus	Diversity in the main focus of the cases, i.e. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ direct energy production and consumption, ➤ mobility, and ➤ more holistic cases that nevertheless include a focus on either direct energy production and consumption or mobility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ cc. 2/5 in direct energy production and consumption, ➤ cc. 1/5 mobility, and ➤ cc. 2/5 holistic in each country
3. individual/collective	Diversity in terms of individual vs. collective cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Cc. 1-2/10 individual, and ➤ 8-9/10 collective cases in each country
4. ideal types (D2.2)	There is also need for diversity in the ideal types identified in the conceptual typology (with view to including cases that are not yet (clearly) identified as types in the typology)	find (an) example(s) of each ideal type if available
5. additional criteria	Diversity also need to be strived for in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ gender focus in cases, ➤ focus on disadvantaged groups (e.g. those in energy poverty, minorities), ➤ behaviour or practice change / low-tech / high-tech, ➤ urban and rural cases, ➤ latent and manifest forms of ENCI 	find (an) example(s) of each if available

Table 4: Summary of the sampling strategy developed for the mapping of ENCI

Lastly, an attempt will be made to find less manifest or latent forms of ENCI, those that are more difficult to find either because they are very new in their given contexts and still very much in the development stage, or do not make an explicit effort to communicate, etc. (see more details about latent forms of ENCI in Pel et al., 2021 and Pel and Kemp, 2020).

At the internal training workshop for ENCI mapping members of the consortium identified a variety of ways of finding latent forms of ENCI, these are summarised in Annex II.

4. The ENCI mapping methodology

The mapping is the first stage in the EnergyPROSPECTS project cases and data collection as well as analysis process. The main objective of mapping is to review the landscape of ENCI in Europe, and do so by collecting 500+ cases. It is important to note that as conducting a representative mapping would go beyond the scope of the current project, in line with the research questions, **the overall objective is to map the diversity of the forms of energy citizenship in Europe.**

The main method for this first stage of cases data collection is **(a guided) desk-based research**. As indicated above, the methodology was developed collaboratively by the EnergyPROSPECTS team; however, it was also informed by earlier similar European research, such as carried out in the CONVERGE (FP7)¹, TRANSIT (FP7)², PROSEU (H2020)³ and ENERGISE (H2020)⁴ projects. In the subsequent sections the methodology for mapping ENCI in Europe is introduced.

4.1. Mapping cases of energy citizenship

As indicated in Figure 8 below, depicting the process of ENCI mapping, the methodology is designed to include several cycles of cases data collection and team review in order to achieve the greatest possible coverage and diversity in cases, as well as to ensure that the operationalisation of the conceptual framework and typology is continuously discussed and monitored within the team. This process will also help to achieve a shared understanding and implementation within the team.

In addition to the review meetings, shared support files for search terms and potential cases will also aid the mapping process. These shared files will furthermore ensure that the existing knowledge and experience within the research team is best utilised.

¹ Vadovics et al., 2012 and 2013

² Jorgensen et al., 2014

³ Campos, Marín-González, 2020 and Horstink et al., 2019

⁴ Jensen et al., 2017a and 2017b

Figure 8: The ENCI mapping process

As shown in Figure 8, the first step in the mapping process requires that relevant cases of ENCI be identified. Taking the definition of ENCI and cases of ENCI as a starting point and guided by the sampling strategy, members of the research team will first review selected databases of sustainable energy initiatives. Some of these databases were already identified at the proposal writing stage, and some were added later. These **databases are intended to inspire and kick-start the search for cases**, and are as follows:

- ENERGISE database: including mainly collective cases from all European countries, the online database is available at <http://www.energise-project.eu/projects> and Jensen et al. (2017); but the research team also has access to the more detailed database of cases data
- EUSEW award winners and finalists (4-5 categories/year, very different cases including both individual and collective cases): <https://eusew.eu/about-awards-competition>)
- RESCOOP network (only collective cases): <https://www.rescoop.eu/network>
- Transition Town network (only collective cases) <https://transitionnetwork.org/transition-near-me/>
- selected cases from the TRANSIT project, available at <http://www.transitsocialinnovation.eu/discover-our-cases-2>

- Transformative Cities (Atlas of Utopias) <https://transformativecities.org/atlas-of-utopias/>
- ETIP SNET Energy stories <https://www.etip-snet.eu/etip-snet-energy-stories/>
- Cases listed on a map of energy democracy initiatives available at <https://energy-democracy.net/map/>
- SI-drive database: <https://www.si-drive.eu/mapping-social-innovations/>

In addition to using the databases, members of the research team are also encouraged to:

- check whether local, country or region-specific similar databases are available; and
- contact professional networks related to energy citizenship in the countries they are responsible for (see Annex I).

4.2. Data to be collected

When planning the data collection survey, several different data needs had to be considered:

1. basic data on cases of ENCI to provide a basis for later creating the public database online with easily understandable information on the cases (geography, main actors, main objectives, etc.), as well as to enable a statistical analysis;
2. data needed for further cases analysis work in subsequent work packages;
3. data to enable the operationalisation of the conceptual framework and typology, related to the seven main distinctions of energy citizenship identified in Pel et al. (2021) as well as to the attributes of the typology matrix as defined in Debourdeau et al. (2021);
4. additional data to enable further analysis of the cases on their contribution to the overall sustainability of the energy system, i.e. the decarbonisation of the energy system. Additional literature from connecting or similar studies informed creating the questions for the relevant parts of the survey (Pelenc, Ballet, 2015; Lorek, Vadovics, 2018; UNEP, 2020; Vadovics, Milton, 2018); and
5. finally, information to help assess whether cases would be appropriate for detailed case study research in Stage 2 of the data collection process.

Table 5 summarizes the data collection survey questions that were arrived at after several commenting and discussion cycles among the EnergyPROSPECTS consortium (see Figure 8 on the specifics of this process).

D.3.1 Methodology for meta-analysis of energy citizenship

Type of information	No. of Q	Question	Response type	Compulsory question	Notes
Basic information about researcher	1	Which EP partner organization do you represent?	Dropdown list	*	
	2	Name of main researcher responsible for data collection for the case:	Single Textbox	*	
	3	Email of main researcher responsible for the case:	Single Textbox	*	
Checking for the project sampling categories	4	What is (was, if it is a concluded case) in the main focus of the case? Please select one from the list bearing in mind that here we are checking the focus for our sampling strategy, so this list is deliberately simplistic. Also, if you decide to select "none of the above", please refer to our sampling strategy and reconsider whether the case is appropriate for our research.	Multiple Choice	*	
	5	Is it an individual or a collective ENCI case?	Multiple Choice	*	
	6	Where is the target area of the case? (e.g. if the case organizers are in a city, but they work with women in rural areas, then you need to select "rural area")	Multiple Choice	*	
	7	Please check if the following apply to the case. Please select as many as apply. Here, we are still checking for our sampling strategy categories, so please don't worry that this question is a little simplistic.	Checkboxes	*	
Basic information about the case	8	How and where did you find the case? Please select from the list.	Multiple Choice	*	
	9	What is (was, if it is a concluded case) the title of the case in English?	Single Textbox	*	
	10	What is/was the title in the original language if available?	Single Textbox	*	
	11	Please provide a brief overview / summary description of the case in 3-5 sentences. Please be aware that this summary will appear in the online database, so its objective is to present the case to an audience who may never have heard about it before.	Single Textbox	*	
	12	In your own words, please explain briefly why you think this is a case of ENCI (i.e. why have you decided to include it in our database)? Please note that at this point you are not asked to place the case in the conceptual typology, but to simply explain in 1-2 sentences why you think this case should be included in our mapping of ENCI in EnergyPROSPECTS.	Single Textbox	*	
	13	Where is/was the case based? (country)	Dropdown list	*	
	14	Is/was the case active (i.e. operates/operated) in other countries as well?	Multiple Choice	*	
	15	Please select from the list in which countries the case is active. Please select all that apply.	Checkboxes		only appears if certain answers are selected for 14
	16	Please provide the name of a contact person if available.	Single Textbox		
	17	Please provide an email address to the contact person if available:	Single Textbox		

D.3.1 Methodology for meta-analysis of energy citizenship

Type of information	No. of Q	Question	Response type	Compulsory question	Notes
Basic information about the case	18	Public email address for contacting the case (this can also be a general email address like info@... or similar):	Single Textbox	*	
	19	Postcode and/or name of the settlement (village, town, city, etc.) where the case is/was based. If it is a country case or a case covering a group of countries, please provide the name of the country or group of countries, or the most relevant geographical entity.	Single Textbox	*	
	20	Please select whether the case has any of the following: (Please select all that apply).	Checkboxes	*	
	21	If yes to website: please provide web address of the case:	Single Textbox		only appears if YES is selected for website for 20
	22	If yes to any of the social media: please provide the social media page address(es) of the case:	Single Textbox		only appears if YES is selected for social media for 20
	23	If yes to YouTube channel: please provide a link to the channel:	Single Textbox		only appears if YES is selected for YouTube for 20
Overview, motivation, objectives	24	Why did the case start, what inspired its conception, what motivated its start? Please select max. 3 from the list, including the choice of adding your own summary of the motivation. Please focus on the main motivations.	Checkboxes	*	
	25	What do the actors involved in the case want to achieve (or did, if it is a completed case)? What are/were the main objectives? Please select max. 3 from the list, including adding objectives that are not listed here.	Checkboxes	*	
	26	Did the objectives change during the history of the case?	Multiple Choice	*	
	27	If you selected "yes" for 26 or if you wish to add anything on the objectives, please explain and share briefly in the textbox.	Single Textbox		only appears if YES is selected for website for 26
Start and conclusion of the case	28	When was the case started?	Dropdown list	*	
	29	Is the case currently active? (If it is a case of an individual, is the individual engaged in his/her energy citizenship activities now?)	Multiple Choice	*	
	30	If no: when was it concluded, when did it stop to operate?	Dropdown list		only appears if NO is selected for website for 29

D.3.1 Methodology for meta-analysis of energy citizenship

Type of information	No. of Q	Question	Response type	Compulsory question	Notes
Actors	31	Who or which actors initiated the case? Please select more if relevant. If the case is a project in an organisation, please consider the actors initiating the case, and not the organisation.	Checkboxes	*	
	32	If available, please provide the name of the actors who initiated the case' (e.g. John Lenon, municipality of X town, X NGO, etc.).	Single Textbox		
	33	Who and/or which actors are currently involved in the case (or were involved if it is a completed case)? Please select all that are relevant.	Checkboxes	*	
	34	Please add any comments you may have about actors involved in the case.	Single Textbox		
Scale of activities	35	At which scale does the case itself currently operate or involve actors (or operated / involved actors when it was concluded)? Please select all that apply based on how the case defines this, if this information is available.	Checkboxes	*	
Organisational form, structure	36	What is the current organisational form/structure of the case (or was the organisation form when the case was concluded)? Please select one from the list. NB: Please note that here we are not asking about the actors, but the form of working and operating specifically for the case. So, if the case is a community energy case, it could be an NGO, a non-profit company (social enterprise), a cooperative, an SME, etc. And if the case is a project of an organisation, do not fill this in for the organisation, but the case (i.e. select project/programme within an organisation).	Multiple Choice	*	
	37	Did the organisational form of the case changed during its history?	Multiple Choice	*	
	38	If yes and if information is available, please provide details of the organisational change briefly (e.g. actors first engaged as an informal community group, and then an NGO with a legal identity was established).	Single Textbox		only appears if YES is selected for website for 37
	39	Is/was the case part of a network of similar initiatives? (e.g. Transition Towns, RESCOOPs, eco villages, climate-friendly municipalities, etc.)	Multiple Choice	*	
	40	If yes, please provide the name of the network if known.	Single Textbox		only appears if YES is selected for website for 39

D.3.1 Methodology for meta-analysis of energy citizenship

Type of information	No. of Q	Question	Response type	Compulsory question	Notes
Change, growth, contraction, afterlife	41	Did the case experience change (if it is already concluded, during its operation), e.g. growth or contraction in any aspect? E.g. in terms of the number or type of actors involved, income/funding, scale of activities or any other aspect?	Multiple Choice	*	
	42	In which aspect did the case experience change, growth or contraction? Please select all relevant aspects from the list	Checkboxes		only appears if certain answers are selected for 41
	43	Please share briefly any additional comments you may have related to aspects of change (growth, contraction, etc.) experienced by the case.	Single Textbox		
	44	If the case is already concluded, did it have any afterlife, continuation in a different form/project, etc.?	Multiple Choice		
	45	Please explain briefly the afterlife, etc. of the case.	Single Textbox		only appears if YES is selected for website for 44
Funding	46	What is (was, if the case is already concluded) the primary / main source of funding for this case (i.e. the source where they have the most income from)? Please select one from the list.	Multiple Choice	*	
	47	Are/were there any other sources of funding for this case? Please select as many as relevant from the list. Please don't repeat the major/main source of funding here if you were able to determine it in the previous question.	Checkboxes	*	
Forms of energy citizenship (ENCI) the case shapes / enables / supports (or shaped / enabled / supported)	48	In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), please place the case (including if it is a case of an individual actor) on a scale of passive-active below, by moving the slider.	Slider	*	
	49	Please explain briefly (in 1-3 sentences) why you placed the case as you did.	Single Textbox	*	
	50	In terms of the forms of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering the private-public distinction, please select which applies most to this particular case, including if it is a case of an individual actor.	Multiple Choice	*	
	51	Please explain your selection in 1-3 sentences.	Single Textbox	*	
	52	In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), please select the appropriate level of hybridity for the case (including if it is a case of an individual actor).	Multiple Choice	*	
53	Please explain briefly (in 1-3 sentences) why you selected the response that you did.	Single Textbox	*		

D.3.1 Methodology for meta-analysis of energy citizenship

Type of information	No. of Q	Question	Response type	Compulsory question	Notes
Forms of energy citizenship (ENCI) the case shapes / enables / supports	54	In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering effective citizen power/ control, please select which applies most to this particular case. If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation provided in D2.2 (Conceptual Typology) (pg. 31).	Multiple Choice	*	
	55	Please briefly (in 1-3 sentences) explain your selection.	Single Textbox	*	
	56	In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering energy justice and equity issues, please select which applies most to this particular case. If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation provided in D2.2 (Conceptual Typology).	Multiple Choice	*	
	57	Please briefly (in 1-3 sentences) explain your selection.	Single Textbox	*	
	58	In terms of form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering environmental sustainability, please select which applies most to this particular case, including if it is a case of an individual actor. If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation provided in D2.2 (Conceptual Typology).	Multiple Choice	*	
	59	Please briefly (in 1-3 sentences) explain your selection, and any other issue that may be important in relation to your selection.	Single Textbox	*	
	60	Does/did the case shape/enable/support ENCI that explicitly recognize the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions (most typically expressed in CO2e)? (e.g. mention of the max. (per capita) carbon footprint, the sustainable carbon footprint, etc.)	Multiple Choice	*	
	61	Are there other ecological limits (e.g. biodiversity loss, deforestation, freshwater use, chemical pollution, etc.) mentioned and recognized as well?	Multiple Choice	*	
	62	Please list which limits are mentioned and/or recognized.	Single Textbox		only appears if YES is selected for website for 61
	63	In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering the laggard - frontrunner distinction, please select which applies most to this particular case, including if it is a case of an individual actor. Please think of your NATIONAL LEVEL context when making your decision.	Multiple Choice	*	

D.3.1 Methodology for meta-analysis of energy citizenship

Type of information	No. of Q	Question	Response type	Compulsory question	Notes
Forms of energy citizenship (ENCI) the case shapes / enables / supports	64	In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering the laggard - frontrunner distinction, please select which applies most to this particular case, including if it is a case of an individual actor. Please think of the EUROPEAN LEVEL context when making your decision.	Multiple Choice	*	
	65	Please explain your selection for the questions on the laggard-frontrunner distinction. If you selected a different response for the two levels (national and European), please explain briefly why.	Single Textbox	*	
	66	In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), please place the case (including if it is a case of an individual actor) on a scale of pragmatic - transformative change, by moving the slider. If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation of the terms provided in D2.1 (Chapter 3.7).	Slider	*	
	67	Please briefly (in 1-3 sentences) explain why you placed the case as you did.	Single Textbox	*	
	68	In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), please select which applies most to this particular case in terms of contesting the current energy system, including if it is a case of an individual actor. If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation provided in D2.2 (Conceptual Typology).	Multiple Choice	*	
	69	Please briefly (in 1-3 sentences) explain your selection.	Single Textbox		only appears if certain answers are selected for 68
Outcomes, impacts, progress towards objectives	70	Is information about the outcomes of the case available? (e.g. about amount of energy generated, number of actors involved, meetings organized, changes achieved, etc.)	Multiple Choice	*	
	71	If yes, please provide some details briefly (we will investigate this aspect more in the detailed case study stage, so there is no need to provide a lot of details).	Single Textbox		only appears if YES is selected for website for 70
	72	Have the impacts of the case and/or its progress towards its objectives been evaluated?	Multiple Choice	*	
	73	Please explain briefly how (e.g. through sustainability reporting on an annual basis, by using indicators on X and publishing them, etc.). You don't need to be very detailed, just indicate the main method and what has been evaluated briefly.	Single Textbox		only appears if certain answers are selected for 72
	74	If impacts were evaluated, who performed the evaluation?	Single Textbox		only appears if 73 appears

D.3.1 Methodology for meta-analysis of energy citizenship

Type of information	No. of Q	Question	Response type	Compulsory question	Notes
Placement in conceptual typology	75	Considering the main (or only) type of ENCI the case shapes/enables/supports, which ideal type of ENCI would you associate it with? Please indicate in the matrix, referring to the typology matrix of ideal types developed in D2.2. Please select one option only. If you find that the case cannot be assigned predominantly to any of the ideal types in the matrix, please select N/A and then provide a brief (in 2-3 sentences) explanation under "Other".	Matrix / Rating Scale	*	
	76	If relevant for this case, which other ideal-type(s) of ENCI does the case shape/enable/support? Please indicate as many as are relevant for the case, referring to the typology matrix of ideal types developed in D2.2. If different types (not yet in the typology) or no other ideal type(s) are relevant for this case, please select "N/A" and then provide a brief explanation under "Other".	Matrix / Rating Scale	*	
	77	If you selected additional ideal types for your case, please provide a brief explanation for why you selected these for this particular case.	Single Textbox		
	78	If you like, please provide comments about your experience of using the typology as you have tried to apply it to this particular case and the forms of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports.	Single Textbox		
Recommendation for detailed study	79	Would you recommend this case for detailed study in our project?	Multiple Choice	*	
	80	Please provide a brief explanation for your recommendation.	Single Textbox	*	
	81	Is sufficient information readily available about the case?	Multiple Choice	*	
	82	Do you have existing contact with the case owners? (e.g. in case you already worked with them in a different project, you know them through professional networks, etc.)	Multiple Choice	*	
	83	Please list the references you used for filling in this mapping questionnaire, including websites, articles, reports, etc.	Single Textbox	*	

D.3.1 Methodology for meta-analysis of energy citizenship

Type of information	No. of Q	Question	Response type	Compulsory question	Notes
Picture (for online database and publications)	84	Please share at least 1 picture representing the case.	File Upload		
	85	If you have more pictures to share, please upload one more here, and then upload the rest in this folder https://bit.ly/3diZXLX :	File Upload		
	86	What is the source of the picture (or pictures if you shared more)? Please include the link(s) or name(s) of source(s).	Single Textbox		
	87	Have you already obtained permission to use the picture(s)? (We need to obtain permission to use pictures in our materials, so if you do not yet have the permission, you will need to obtain it.)	Multiple Choice		
Closing		Please leave any additional comments you may have about the survey, the case, or anything related to your experience that may be useful for further work and analysis. E.g. have there been places in the survey where you have found it particularly hard to respond? or something that you particularly liked about your experience?	Single Textbox		

Table 5: Summary of data to be collected during the ENCI mapping process

4.3. The data collection tool

Data collection will be carried out through using an online survey tool, SurveyMonkey. This tool allows some level of automatic analysis that will support the data collection review cycles. Furthermore, the collected data can be easily transferred to other databases for subsequent analysis. The final data collection survey template from SurveyMonkey can be seen in Annex IV.

The online tool can be accessed at <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/ENCImapping500>

5. Research ethics considerations

All research activities described in the methodology will be carried out in agreement with the *Research ethics guidelines* of the EnergyPROSPECTS project (Vadovics et al., 2021). Furthermore, although the mapping of ENCI only requires the review of publicly available resources related to cases of ENCI, members of the consortium will make an effort to notify all case owners of their inclusion in the online public database (to this end, the consortium is collecting publicly available contact details for all the cases). Case owners will also be given the opportunity to correct the data published in the online database if required.

All information gathered through the ENCI mapping survey will be handled in accordance with GDPR guidelines and the data management guidelines laid down in the EnergyPROSPECTS project (see the Data management plan in NUI Galway, 2021 and the Research ethics guidelines in Vadovics et al., 2021). The information derived from the survey is purely used within the frame of the EnergyPROSPECTS project and will not be provided to any third parties. Identifiable data will be safely stored.

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Annex I:**The division of countries between partners for ENCI mapping**

Country group	Countries	Partner
EU	Hungary Denmark Poland Slovakia	GDI (4 + 3)
EEA	Norway Iceland	
accession	Turkey	
EU	Bulgaria Slovenia Croatia	ARC (3 + 4)
accession	Serbia Bosnia Montenegro North Macedonia	
EU	Netherlands Greece Cyprus	UM (3)
EU	Ireland	NUIG (2 + 1)
EEA	Switzerland UK	
EU	Germany Austria Malta	TUB (2 + 1)
EU	Belgium Luxembourg Check Republic	ULB (3)
EU	Spain Portugal Romania	UDC (3)
EU	France Italy Sweden Finland	JDI (4)
EU	Latvia Lithuania Estonia	UL (3)

Annex II: How to find latent cases? Tips from the EnergyPROSPECTS team

Annex III:

Examples of individual forms of energy citizenship and how to find them

Examples for individual ENCI cases	How to find them?
<p>People building passive, active, autonomous houses, or straw bale houses, etc.</p> <p>People living self-sufficiently (similar or the same as autonomous house, but framed differently)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • search for people who are very committed and/or proud of their achievements and communicate about them (e.g. they have a blog, vlog, run a social media page, there are media stories about them, etc.) • find media stories, podcasts, reports about these people, listed as examples, often also in projects (e.g. NZEB related open door or other open door projects) • find projects (either EU, national or local) which organized these people and created databases on them, e.g. open house/open door databases, renovation or equipment exchange projects
<p>People being very committed to reducing their carbon footprint in various ways and communicating about it</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • find projects (either EU, national or local) which organized these people and created databases on them, e.g. open house/open door databases, renovation or equipment exchange projects
<p>Certain green influencers - those that are not celebrities, but everyday people not even necessarily setting out to be influencers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search online, incl. social media, be aware of different types: simple life (low-tech and behaviour change), high tech, etc.
<p>Scientists deciding to become activists in various ways, e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • joining and writing about their stories in relation to the organization Scientist for Extinction Rebellion, or • starting a blog and talking about carbon footprint reduction, need for change, etc. • speaking up at events regularly, appearing in online talks, podcasts, etc. • talking to the media 	<p>Search online in your country, but see some examples here:</p> <p>There is an increasing number of news stories, personal blogs, interviews, etc. (e.g. for blog/tips, etc. see example HERE, or HERE: from IPCC lawyer to activist).</p> <p>See summary articles HERE or HERE.</p>

Annex IV:

The online SurveyMonkey data collection template

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492

EnergyPROSPECTS - Energy Citizenship (ENCI) Mapping tool

Task 3.1 and 3.2

Dear Partners, dear Colleagues involved in mapping ENCI in Europe,

Welcome to the online ENCI mapping tool! The mapping is the first stage in the EP project cases and data collection as well as analysis process.

With the help of the mapping tool, our main objective in the EnergyPROSPECTS project in this task is to map the landscape for the diversity of energy citizenship (ENCI) in Europe, and do so by collecting 500+ cases.

It is important to remember that we are not attempting to do a representative survey of the cases or to map each and every case of ENCI in European countries as these would go beyond the scope of the EnergyPROSPECTS project. Instead, we wish to discover and map the diversity of existing forms of ENCI, as outlined in our [sampling strategy](#), which we are asking you to please study before you start the case collection and inputting cases in the tool.

The main method for this first stage is a **(guided) desk-based research**, at times perhaps supplemented with a quick follow-up call. The aim of such calls is to quickly check data otherwise obtained, ask for documents, and perhaps specify some information, but not to interview the case contact persons (which will come at a later stage).

This methodology means that we may not always be able to respond to all questions in the mapping survey. However, at this stage this is fine, you will always find a response choice that allows you to say "I don't know / there is not enough information available about this aspect at this stage".

And some practical information:

- if a question is marked *, you have to provide some sort of a response;
- if a question includes [OPEN DATABASE], it means that we are going to publish the information in the interactive database on ENCI at a later stage. However, you will have the chance to review your responses before this is done.

Finally, a reminder: **what is a case in EnergyPROSPECTS mapping of energy citizenship?**

A case of ENCI

1. is a constellation of actors (in a certain context) that
 - enables/supports citizens to become active private and/or public energy citizens;
 - acts as a collective energy citizen by contributing to change of the energy system
2. includes individual energy citizens and how they realize their potential in a private, public or organisational setting.

1

Please note that as agreed, we are reviewing **currently ongoing as well as concluded (no later than in 2015) cases** in the mapping exercise (please see our [guidance document](#) for more details).

All information gathered through the survey will be handled in accordance with GDPR guidelines and the data management guidelines laid down in the EnergyPROSPECTS project (please see D1.2 and D1.5).

The information derived from this survey is purely used within the frame of the EnergyPROSPECTS project. Information will not be provided to any third parties. Identifiable data will be safely stored. In case have any questions or concerns in terms of using the data, please contact GreenDependent.

the GreenDependent EnergyPROSPECTS team
info@greendependent.org

The sole responsibility for the content of this survey lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the INEA nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

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EnergyPROSPECTS - Energy Citizenship (ENCI) Mapping tool

Basic information about the researcher

*** 1. Which EP partner organization do you represent?**

*** 2. Name of main researcher responsible for data collection for the case:**

*** 3. Email of main researcher responsible for the case:**

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EnergyPROSPECTS - Energy Citizenship (ENCI) Mapping tool

Checking for the project sampling categories

*** 4. What is (was, if it is a concluded case) in the main focus of the case? Please select one from the list bearing in mind that here we are checking the focus for our sampling strategy, so this list is deliberately simplistic. Also, if you decide to select "none of the above", please refer to our [sampling strategy](#) and reconsider whether the case is appropriate for our research.**

- direct energy production and/or consumption
- mobility
- holistic/focus on broader change (select this if (1) the case focuses on both of the above, (2) e.g. carbon footprint reduction, which includes all aspects // lifestyle change approach // settlement-level energy transition // just energy transition)
- none of the above

*** 5. Is it an individual or a collective ENCI case?**

- individual
- collective

*** 6. Where is the target area of the case based?
(e.g. if the case organizers are in a city, but they work with women in rural areas, then you need to select "rural area")**

- urban area
- peri-urban area
- rural area, including remote communities, islands, etc.
- several or all of the above
- this distinction is not relevant to this case (e.g. it is a virtual case)
- other, please explain:

*** 7. Please check if the following apply to the case. Please select as many as apply. Here we are still checking for our sampling strategy categories, so please don't worry that this question is a little simplistic/limiting.**

- It has a gender focus (e.g. focus on gender equity, focus on women, etc.)
- It focuses on issues related to disadvantaged groups (e.g. those in energy poverty, minorities, etc.)
- None of these apply to the case

5

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EnergyPROSPECTS - Energy Citizenship (ENCI) Mapping tool

Basic information about the case

*** 8. How and where did you find the case? Please select from the list.**

- I knew about it from other work/projects
- It is my own/our organisation's own project/programme (or part of it)
- from the ENERGISE database
- from another database suggested by GDI
- through Internet search
- I contacted an expert/organisation and they suggested it
- it was suggested by an EP project partner colleague
- other, please provide details:

*** 9. [OPEN DATABASE] What is (or was, if it is a concluded case) the title of the case in English?**

10. [OPEN DATABASE] What is/was the title in the original language if available?

*** 11. [OPEN DATABASE] Please provide a brief overview / summary description of the case in 3-5 sentences . Please be aware that this summary will appear in the online database, so its objective is to present the case to an audience who may never have heard about it before.**

*** 12. In your own words, please explain briefly why you think this is a case of ENCI (i.e. why have you decided to include it in our database)? Please note that at this point you are not asked to place the case in the conceptual typology, but to simply explain in 2-3 sentences why you think this case should be included in our mapping of ENCI in EnergyPROSPECTS.**

Please remember that in EP, 'Energy citizenship refers to forms of civic involvement that pertain to the development of a more sustainable and democratic energy system. Beyond its manifest forms, ENCI also comprises various latent forms: it is an ideal that can be lived up to and realised to varying degrees, according to different framework conditions and states of empowerment.'

*** 13. [OPEN DATABASE] Where is/was the case based? (country)**

*** 14. Is/was the case active (i.e. operates/operated) in other countries as well?**

- Yes
- Not currently, but it was in the past
- Not currently, but it will be in the future
- No
- I don't know

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15. [OPEN DATABASE] If active in other countries, (currently, in the past or in the future) please select from the list in which countries. Please select all that apply.

- Albania
- Austria
- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Croatia
- Cyprus
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Estonia
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Hungary
- Iceland
- Ireland
- Italy
- Latvia
- Liechtenstein
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Malta
- Montenegro
- Netherlands
- North Macedonia
- Norway
- Poland

- Portugal
- Romania
- Serbia
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Turkey
- United Kingdom
- Other, please list:

16. Please provide the name of a contact person if available.
(This information does not need to be available publicly for the case, you can rely on your own information as well. Also, please note that this information will not be made public, i.e. included in the open database later, this is only for us if we wish to contact the case for more information):

17. Please provide an email address for the contact person if available:

*** 18. [OPEN DATABASE] Public email address for contacting the case (this can also be a general email address like info@... or similar):**

*** 19. [OPEN DATABASE] Postcode and/or name of the settlement (village, town, city, etc.) where the case is/was based.**

If it is a country case or a case covering a group of countries, please provide the name of the country or group of countries, or the most relevant geographical entity.

*** 20. [OPEN DATABASE] Please select whether the case has any of the following. Please select all that apply.**

- Website
- Facebook
- Twitter
- Linked-in
- Instagram
- YouTube channel
- Newsletter
- This case does not use any of these communication channels.
- Other, please list:

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21. [OPEN DATABASE] If yes to website: please provide web address of the case:

22. [OPEN DATABASE] If yes to any of the social media: please provide the social media page address(es) of the case:

23. [OPEN DATABASE] If yes to YouTube channel, please provide a link to the channel:

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Overview, motivation, objectives

*** 24. Why did the case start, what inspired its conception, what motivated its start?**
Please select max. 3 from the list, including the choice of adding your own summary of the motivation. Please focus on the main motivating, driving factors and causes. Do not worry if you don't find the options you need, feel free to select "Other".

In some cases this question will be easy to answer as the motivation is clearly, stated on the website of the case or in materials related to the case. However, often it will be challenging to answer as only objectives (i.e. aims to achieve) will be communicated, so please feel free to select the option "the motivation for the case is not known". In other cases the distinction between the motivation and objectives is somewhat blurred and not so clear, in which cases please do not worry about selecting similar responses for this question and the next one on objectives.

- recognition of own responsibility
- recognition of the seriousness of climate change
- realization of a particular energy related injustice
- frustration due to lack of action by decision makers
- action/example shown by a person known by the initiator(s) of the case
- inspiration by a similar case elsewhere
- community building
- increasing self-sufficiency
- contribute to the energy transition
- discontent because energy transition is not going fast enough/ is not tackling fundamental problems of the current energy system
- produce and/or use renewable energy
- increasing public involvement
- availability of incentive (e.g. funding for renovation, funding for campaign, etc.)
- need to respond to local/national/etc. demand
- the motivation for the case is not known or cannot be defined at this stage
- other, please explain briefly:

*** 25. What do the actors involved in the case want to achieve (or did, if it is a completed case)? What are/were the main objectives, aims? Please select max. 3 from the list, including adding objectives that are not listed here.**

Do not worry if you don't find the options you need, feel free to select "Other".

- advocacy for a just transition
- supporting, promoting, enabling prosumerism
- promoting and enabling climate action
- ending dependence on fossil fuels / phasing out fossil fuels
- promoting energy saving
- energy justice
- energy democracy
- alleviating energy poverty
- reducing the carbon footprint (of individuals, households, organizations, etc.)
- increasing and/or achieving self-sufficiency
- protest for the energy transition
- protest against an energy related issue (e.g. nuclear energy, wind mills, etc.)
- lobby for a specific institutional act or the revision of an existing act
- action aimed at altering proposed projects of others
- the creation of strategic intelligence via networking activities and products
- encouraging, enabling debate on energy and/or climate issues
- creating and promoting an alternative societal and/or economic model
- other, please summarize briefly:

*** 26. Did the objectives change during the history of the case?**

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

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27. If you selected "yes" for the previous question or if you wish to add anything on the objectives, please explain and share briefly in the textbox.

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Start and conclusion of the case

*** 28. When was the case started?**

*** 29. Is the case currently active? (If it is a case of an individual, is the individual engaged in his/her energy citizenship activities now?)**

Yes

No

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30. If no: when was it concluded, when did it stop to operate?

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Actors

*** 31. Who or which actors initiated the case? Please select more if relevant.**
If the case is a project in an organisation, please consider the actors initiating the case, and not the organisation.

- an individual
- two or more individuals, an informal group of individuals (incl. community group)
- one or more NGO(s)
- one or more non-profit company/enterprise (e.g. a not-for-profit ltd, social enterprise, etc.)
- one or more for-profit company/enterprise
- one or more cooperative
- one or more school or university
- one or more municipality, incl. municipal department or agency
- department, agency or public body of a regional government
- department, agency or public body of a national government
- department, agency of public body of the EU
- a network organization (informal or formal)
- it is not possible to determine who started the case
- others or "not sure", please explain briefly:

32. If available, please provide the name of the actors who initiated the case (e.g. John Lenon, municipality of X town, X NGO, etc.)

*** 33. Who and/or which actors are currently involved in the case (or were involved if it is a completed case)? Please select all that are relevant.**

- an individual
- individuals in a household setting
- individuals in an organizational setting
- a group of individuals (incl. community group)
- a group of households
- NGO(s) (or NPO, association, foundation, charity, etc.)
- one or more non-profit company/enterprise (e.g. not-for-profit ltd, social enterprise, etc.)
- one or more for-profit company/enterprise
- one or more school or university
- municipality, incl. municipal department or agency
- department, agency or public body of a regional government
- department, agency or public body of a national government
- department, agency or public body of the EU
- network organization (informal or formal)
- others, please specify:

34. Please add any comments you may have about actors involved in the case.

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Scale of activities

*** 35. At which scale does the case itself currently operate or involve actors (or operated / involved actors when it was concluded)? Please select all that apply based on how the case defines this, if this information is available.**

- individual or household (e.g. it is a case of an individual or household)
- organisational (i.e. within an organisation, which can be an NGO, corporation, municipality, etc.)
- local (i.e. at a scale smaller than municipal, e.g. local community, neighbourhood, or an apartment block/housing estate)
- municipal (i.e. within the boundaries of a certain city, town, settlement)
- regional
- national
- multi-country (i.e. in more than one country)
- European Union (i.e. in all or most EU member states)
- European (i.e. in all European countries, including EU and non-EU countries)
- other international/global
- other, please explain:

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Organisational form, structure

*** 36. What is the current organisational form/structure of the case (or was the organisation form when the case was concluded)? Please select one from the list. Please note that here we are not asking about the actors, but the form of working and operating specifically for the case. So, if the case is a community energy case, it could be an NGO, a non-profit company (social enterprise), a cooperative, an SME, etc. And if the case is a project of an organisation, do not fill this in for the organisation, but the case (i.e. select "project/programme within an organisation").**

- It is a case of an individual
- It is an informal group (i.e. with no legal identity, e.g. a climate group/club, community group, etc.)
- Informal network (i.e. with no legal identity, e.g. a network of researchers like SCORAI Europe, Scientists for Extinction Rebellion, etc.)
- It is a project/programme within an organisation
- It is a partnership (public, public-private, etc.)
- It is a development trust (mainly in the UK, e.g. community trust association)
- NGO (i.e. not-for-profit organization, an association or a foundation with a legal identity, charity, etc.)
- non-profit company/enterprise (e.g. not-for-profit ltd, social enterprise)
- for-profit company/enterprise (please note this can be of various sizes, e.g. SME, corporation, etc.)
- cooperative
- school or university
- formally established network (i.e. with a legal identity, e.g. Friends of the Earth, ICLEI)
- project consortium
- municipality, incl. municipal department or agency
- department, agency or public body of the regional government
- department, agency of public body of the EU
- the organisational form cannot be determined based on available information
- other, please specify:

*** 37. Did the organisational form of the case change during its history?**

Yes

No

Not relevant

I don't know

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38. If yes and if information is available, please provide details of the organisational change briefly (e.g. actors first engaged as an informal community group, and then an NGO with a legal identity was established).

*** 39. Is/was the case part of a network of similar initiatives? (e.g. Transition Towns, RESCOOPs, eco villages, climate-friendly municipalities, etc.)**

Please note that the organisational form (see questions above) of the case can also be an informal or formal network. Here we are asking whether the case, regardless of its organisational form, is part of a network of similar cases. (Sometimes the organisational form of a case is a network (e.g. Friends of the Earth Hungary, which is a network of NGOs), but it can still be part of a larger network (e.g. Friends of the Earth Hungary is part of Friends of the Earth International).

Yes

No

I don't know (no information is readily available about this)

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40. If yes, please provide the name of the network if known.

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Change, growth, contraction, afterlife

*** 41. Did the case experience change (if it is already concluded, during its operation), e.g. growth or contraction in any aspect?
E.g. in terms of the number or type of actors involved, income/funding, scale of activities or any other aspect?**

There was no change
 It experienced growth
 It became smaller, or contracted
 I don't know (no information is readily available about this aspect)
 Other, please explain briefly

42. In which aspect did the case experience change, growth or contraction? Please select all relevant aspects from the list.

in the number of actors involved
 in the types of actors involved
 in the areas of operation (i.e. multiplication, e.g. it started in one place, and now it is active in several places or vice versa)
 in the scale of operations (i.e. upscaling, e.g. it was a local case and not it's national)
 in the income generated
 in the funding attracted
 in its objectives (reformative versus transformative, incremental versus fundamental/radical change, etc.)
 in its outcomes (e.g. energy produced, carbon footprint reduced)
 other, please explain briefly:

43. Please share briefly any additional comments you may have related to aspects of change (growth, contraction, etc.) experienced by the case.

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44. If the case is already concluded, did it have any afterlife, continuation in a different form/project, etc.?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know / I'm not sure / No information is available about this aspect

45. Please explain briefly the afterlife, etc. of the case.

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Funding

*** 46. What is (was, if the case is already concluded) the primary / main source of funding for this case (i.e. the source where they have the most income from)? Please select one from the list.**

- no finance is/was involved
- the major/main source of funding cannot be determined based on desk-based study
- local public funding (e.g. municipality, local authority)
- national public funding
- European public funding
- funding from a company/enterprise/corporation
- funding from an NGO
- donations
- case owner(s)' private funds including owners' pre-existing funds
- crowdfunding / ethex
- crowdlending
- loan(s)
- cooperative or community shares
- membership fee
- the case owners generating income (selling product (incl. energy), service, etc.)
- volunteers 'donating' their work
- other, please explain briefly:

*** 47. Are/were there any other sources of funding for this case? Please select as many as relevant from the list. Please don't repeat the major/main source of funding here if you were able to determine it in the previous question.**

- there are/were no additional sources of funding for this case
- based on available information, I am not sure if there are/were other sources of funding
- local public funding (e.g. municipal)
- national public funding
- European public funding
- funding from a company/enterprise/corporation
- funding from an NGO
- donations
- case owner(s)' private funds
- crowdfunding / ethex
- crowdlending
- membership fee
- the case owners/participants generating income (selling product, service, etc.)
- volunteers 'donating' their work
- other, please explain briefly:

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Forms of energy citizenship (ENCI) the case shapes / enables / supports (shaped/enabled/supported)

*** 48. In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), please place the case (including if it is a case of an individual actor) on a scale of passive-active below, by moving the slider.**

<p>PASSIVE: Consuming energy... not an ENCI yet, rather, passive consumer of energy due to disempowerment, disillusionment, or disinterest)</p>	<p>ACTIVE: Aware, empowered and active: not only changing individually, and joining others, but activating and empowering others and helping others to become active)</p>
--	--

*** 49. Please explain briefly (in 1-3 sentences) why you placed the case as you did.**

*** 50. In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering the private-public distinction, please select which applies most to this particular case, including if it is a case of an individual actor.**

- Private - individual level** action and change (e.g. individual level action in the home, individual lifestyle change, low-carbon consumption)
- Private - household level** action and change (e.g. household level action, still in the home, including more radical change like prosumerism, energy self-sufficiency)
- Private/public at organisations** - change and action at organisations
- Public, smaller scale** - change and action in smaller groups and/or on a smaller scale (e.g. community groups, local shared-ownership and/or renewable energy projects)
- Public, larger scale** - change and action at district, settlement level or even larger scale, incl. societal (e.g. low-carbon districts/towns, city-level public consultation, protests, transition towns)
- Other, please explain:**

*** 51. Please explain your selection in 1-3 sentences.**

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*** 52. In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), please select the appropriate level of hybridity for the case (including if it is a case of an individual actor).**

By hybridity we mean whether the actors involved in the case are all citizens (no hybridity), or the actors represent various types of individuals and/or organisations, e.g. citizens, municipalities, for-profit organisations, etc. A form of ENCI has low hybridity if less types of (e.g. two) actors are involved, and high hybridity if many different types of actors (and institutional logics) are involved. You can also refer to your response to the question above about actors involved when making your decision here. If you wish to have more background on hybridity, please read Chpt. 3.4 in [D2.1 \(Conceptual framework energy citizenship\)](#).

- no hybridity (only one type of actors/institutional logics are involved or represented by in the case)
- low hybridity (2 or 3 types of actors/institutional logics are involved or represented by in the case)
- medium hybridity (4 or 5 types of actors/institutional logics are involved or represented by in the case)
- high hybridity (more than 5 types of actors/institutional logics are involved or represented by in the case)

*** 53. Please explain briefly (in 1-3 sentences) why you selected the response that you did.**

*** 54. In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering effective citizen power/ control, please select which applies most to this particular case.**

If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation provided in [D2.2 \(Conceptual typology\)](#) (pg. 31.).

NB: It is possible that this aspect is discussed in case related materials, and the evaluation there is different from your own view / a more objective evaluation. Here, please select your response based on the latter, but in the textbox provided for the next question please make sure to mention this discrepancy.

- No effective voice citizen power/control
- Low:** When expressed (e.g., within "invited" deliberative processes), citizens' voices remain hardly heard or taken into account. Being a minority, citizens' voices do not really count or in a voting process, the framings tend to limit the possibility of expressing an opinion.
- Medium:** Citizens can express their views, but their voices are not compulsory (within deliberative, representative or consultative processes). Within organised / participative structures, citizens remain a minority group, i.e., unable to impose their views to other groups.
- High:** Citizens are committed to deeply renew and restructure the energy system, toward a more democratic and sustainable one. Narratives, actions and proposals are part of the contestation of the dominant system, and result in critics and protests against energy policies and actions as well as in forms of engagement that aim at fundamental changes (e.g., achieving autonomy).
- This is a case of an individual actor, so this is not relevant.
- This consideration is not relevant to this case for another reason.
- I don't know / not enough information is available about this aspect.

*** 55. Please briefly (in 1-3 sentences) explain your selection.**

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56. In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering energy justice and equity issues, please select which applies most to this particular case.

If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation provided in [D2.2 \(Conceptual Typology\)](#).

NB: It is possible that this aspect is discussed in case related materials, and the evaluation there is different from your own view / a more objective evaluation. Here, please select your response based on the latter, but in the textbox provided for the next question please make sure to mention this discrepancy.

- Energy justice/equity is not considered
- Low:** Justice or equity are essentially out of scope, or restricted to equal access to markets
- Medium:** Equal access is granted to all concerned citizens, but the framings tend to limit them to a certain geographical area or amount of financial contribution, which does not guarantee "real" equity
- High:** involvement is fully open, without specific belonging conditions. Issues such as energy poverty, gender and inclusivity are taken into account and foster adaptive measures to guarantee more justice/equity
- This is a case of an individual actor, so this is not relevant.
- I don't know / not enough information is available about this aspect.
- There is another consideration/issue that prevents me for categorizing this case as Low/Medium/High in terms of energy justice and equity (please explain below).

*** 57. Please briefly (in 1-3 sentences) explain your selection.**

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*** 58. In terms of form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering environmental sustainability, please select which applies most to this particular case, including if it is a case of an individual actor.**

If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation provided in [D2.2 \(Conceptual Typology\)](#).

NB: It is possible that this aspect is discussed in case related materials, and the evaluation there is different from your own view / a more objective evaluation. Here, please select your response based on the latter, but in the textbox provided for the next question please make sure to mention this discrepancy.

- Environmental sustainability is not considered.
- Low:** If given any consideration, environmental sustainability issues are mostly taken for granted and not explicitly taken into account. In the lowest forms, environmental sustainability tends to be dealt with as a positive or negative externality.
- Medium:** Environmental sustainability is part of the process or initiative, but this concern is addressed in a superficial way (focus on efficiency strategies) and without dedicated assessment. Energy remains the main focus.
- High:** Environmental sustainability is a core issue, which is followed with a holistic strategy (mix of efficiency, consistency and sufficiency measures). Its assessment through indicators is seen as desirable.
- I don't know / not enough information is available about this aspect.

*** 59. Please briefly (in 1-3 sentences) explain your selection, and any other issue that may be important in relation to your selection.**

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*** 60. Does/did the case shape/enable/support ENCI that explicitly recognizes the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions (most typically expressed in CO₂e)? (e.g. mention of the max. (per capita) carbon footprint, the sustainable carbon footprint, etc.)**

- No recognition or mention of carbon limit or sustainable carbon footprint
- Implicit recognition *(No explicit mention of the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions or sustainable carbon footprint. But despite the lack of formal references to either of them, the case is involved in activities to reduce the consumption and/or emission of carbon.)*
- Explicit recognition *(The ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions or sustainable carbon footprint is mentioned in core documents and the actors involved in the case are clearly engaged in attempts to reduce consumption and/or emission of carbon.)*
- Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint *(In addition to mentioning the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions or sustainable carbon footprint, the maximum sustainable carbon footprint and/or emissions are also defined.)*
- I cannot say based on the information available on this aspect.

*** 61. Are there other ecological limits (e.g. biodiversity loss, deforestation, freshwater use, chemical pollution, etc.) mentioned and recognized as well? ([Here](#) you can find more information about ecological limits - or planetary boundaries.)**

- Yes
- No
- I don't know / there is no information readily available about this aspect

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62. If yes, please list which limits are mentioned and/or recognized:

*** 63. In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering the laggard - frontrunner distinction, please select which applies most to this particular case, including if it is a case of an individual actor. Please think of your NATIONAL LEVEL context when making your decision.**

If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation of the terms provided in [D2.1 \(Chapter 3.8\)](#).

- frontrunner (~ unleashes the change process, starts the innovation, whether technological or social, and takes its through the first difficult stage, i.e. pioneers trend-setters, those who wish to lead and/or have the resources to lead the change process)
- early adopter (~ opinion leaders who become enthusiastic about new products/ways of doing things/solutions, etc., share their benefits with others and adopt first)
- early majority (~ adopt early, but deliberate, less venturesome and independent than earlier adopters)
- late majority (~ only adopt change when there is a strong feeling of being left behind or missing out)
- laggard / late adopter (~ traditional, slow to change, not yet in a position to change, or those who are resisting change, or who do not wish to 'adopt' and change)
- I don't know / I cannot determine based on available data and information

*** 64. In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), considering the laggard - frontrunner distinction, please select which applies most to this particular case, including if it is a case of an individual actor. Please think of the EUROPEAN LEVEL context when making your decision.**

If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation of the terms provided in [D2.1 \(Chapter 3.8\)](#).

- frontrunner (~ unleashes the change process, starts the innovation, whether technological or social, and takes its through the first difficult stage, i.e. pioneers trend-setters, those who wish to lead and/or have the resources to lead the change process)
- early adopter (~ opinion leaders who become enthusiastic about new products/ways of doing things/solutions, etc., share their benefits with others and adopt first)
- early majority (~ adopt early, but deliberate, less venturesome and independent than earlier adopters)
- late majority (~ only adopt change when there is a strong feeling of being left behind or missing out)
- laggard / late adopter (~ traditional, slow to change, not yet in a position to change, or those who are resisting change, or who do not wish to 'adopt' and change)
- I don't know / I cannot determine based on available data and information

*** 65. Please explain your selection for the questions on the laggard-frontrunner distinction. If you selected a different response for the two levels (national and European), please explain briefly why.**

*** 66. In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), please place the case (including if it is a case of an individual actor) on a scale of pragmatic - transformative change, by moving the slider. If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation of the terms provided in [D2.1 \(Chapter 3.7\)](#).**

PRAGMATIC: pragmatic involvement, often involvement within "concrete projects" or activities, often characterised by pre-occupation with technology and efficiency

TRANSFORMATIVE: transformative involvement, embracing broader energy transition goals and climate change, concern with and focus on energy democracy and/or sufficiency

*** 67. Please briefly (in 1-3 sentences) explain why you placed the case as you did.**

*** 68. In terms of the form of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports (or shaped/enabled/supported), please select which applies most to this particular case in terms of contesting the current energy system, including if it is a case of an individual actor.**

If needed, please refer to the more detailed explanation provided in [D2.2 \(Conceptual Typology\)](#).

- This case does not contest the current energy system.
- Low:** Citizen involvement/action is essentially system-confirming, which means that citizens generally go along with the basic structures of the energy system.
- Medium:** Some system-contesting aspects are part of the process, yet not really appropriated by citizens or considered as a full part of their involvement. Contestation of the system remains "idealistic" or even "utopic", and is not really meant to come into being.
- High:** Citizens are committed to deeply renew and restructure the energy system, toward a more democratic and sustainable one. Narratives, actions and proposals are part of the contestation of the dominant system, and result in critics and protests against energy policies and actions as well as in forms of engagement that aim at fundamental changes (e.g., achieving autonomy).
- I don't know / not enough information is available about this aspect.

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69. Please briefly (in 1-3 sentences) explain your selection.

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Outcomes, impacts, progress towards objectives		
<p>* 70. Is information about the outcomes of the case available? (e.g. about amount of energy generated, number of actors involved, meetings organized, changes achieved, etc.)</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="radio"/> No</p> <p><input type="radio"/> I don't know (there is no information readily available about this)</p>		

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71. If yes, please provide some details briefly (we will investigate this aspect more in the detailed case study stage, so there is no need to provide a lot of details).

*** 72. Have the impacts of the case and/or its progress towards its objectives been evaluated?**

- Yes, both impact and progress towards reaching objectives
- Yes, but only impact
- Yes, but only progress towards reaching objectives
- No
- I don't know (there is no information readily available about this)

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73. If yes, please explain briefly how (e.g. through sustainability reporting on an annual basis, by using indicators on X and publishing them, etc.). You don't need to be very detailed, just indicate the main method and what has been evaluated briefly.

74. If impacts were evaluated, who performed the evaluation?

- Case owners
- Case owners and beneficiaries together
- Evaluators commissioned by case owners
- Evaluation by researchers/organization independent of the case
- I don't know (no information is readily available about this)
- Other, please provide brief details:

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Placement in conceptual typology

[Empty content area]

*** 75. Considering the main (or only) type of ENCI the case shapes/enables/supports, which ideal type of ENCI would you associate it with? Please indicate in the matrix, referring to the [typology matrix of ideal types developed in D2.2](#) . Please select one option only.**
If you find that the case cannot be assigned predominantly to any of the ideal types in the matrix, please select N/A and then provide a brief (in 2-3 sentences) explanation under "Other".

AGENCY		INDIVIDUAL			COLLECTIVE	
OUTCOME ORIENTATION	PRIVATE (HOUSEHOLD)	ORGANISATIONALLY EMBEDDED (E.G., WORKPLACE)	PUBLIC	CITIZEN-BASED AND HYBRID	SOCIAL MOVEMENTS	
REFORMATIVE 	1. DO THEIR BIT (in the household) Complying with the green energy transition	3. DO THEIR BIT (within organisations) Energy citizenship within organisations	5. MAKE THEIR VOICE HEARD Participating in societal energy discussions	7. DO THEIR SHARE Joining green energy projects	9. DO THE JOB Facilitating the energy transition through alignment activities	
TRANSFORMATIVE 	2. DO THEIR OWN (in the household) The change-making energy citizen	4. DO IT THEIR WAY (within organisations) The energy-related change maker in organisations	6. MAKE THEIR VOTE COUNT Mobilising votes for energy transition	8. GO AHEAD Building, expanding and linking citizen-based organisational forms	10. MAKE THEIR CLAIM Protesting against the current energy system	

	Individual - Private	Individual - Organizational	Individual - Public	Collective - Citizen-based and Hybrid	Collective - Social movements	N/A
Reformative (incremental change, low energy democracy, shallow env. sustainability)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Transformative (radical change, high energy democracy, deep env. sustainability)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other - if you selected "N/A", please indicate and explain here why you think your case does not fit any of the ideal types.

*** 76. If relevant for this case, which other ideal-type(s) of ENCI does the case shape/enable/support? Please indicate as many as are relevant for the case, referring to the [typology matrix of ideal types developed in D2.2](#).
If different types (not yet in the typology) or no other ideal type(s) are relevant for this case, please select "N/A" and then provide a brief explanation under "Other".**

AGENCY		INDIVIDUAL			COLLECTIVE	
OUTCOME ORIENTATION						
	PRIVATE (HOUSEHOLD)	ORGANISATIONALLY EMBEDDED (E.G., WORKPLACE)	PUBLIC	CITIZEN-BASED AND HYBRID	SOCIAL MOVEMENTS	
REFORMATIVE 	1. DO THEIR BIT (in the household) Complying with the green energy transition	3. DO THEIR BIT (within organisations) Energy citizenship within organisations	5. MAKE THEIR VOICE HEARD Participating in societal energy discussions	7. DO THEIR SHARE Joining green energy projects	9. DO THE JOB Facilitating the energy transition through alignment activities	
TRANSFORMATIVE 	2. DO THEIR OWN (in the household) The change-making energy citizen	4. DO IT THEIR WAY (within organisations) The energy-related change maker in organisations	6. MAKE THEIR VOTE COUNT Mobilising votes for energy transition	8. GO AHEAD Building, expanding and linking citizen-based organisational forms	10. MAKE THEIR CLAIM Protesting against the current energy system	

	Individual - Private	Individual - Organizational	Individual - Public	Collective - Citizen-based and Hybrid	Collective - Social movements	N/A
Reformative (incremental change, low energy democracy, shallow env. sustainability)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Transformative (radical change, high energy democracy, deep env. sustainability)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other - please explain briefly here if no additional ideal types are relevant for this case, and/or new types would need to be established.

77. If you selected additional ideal types for your case, please provide a brief explanation for why you selected these for this particular case.

78. If you like, please provide comments about your experience of using the typology as you have tried to apply it to this particular case and the forms of ENCI it shapes/enables/supports.

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Recommendation for detailed study

*** 79. Would you recommend this case for detailed study in our project?**

Yes

No

Maybe

*** 80. Please provide a brief explanation for your recommendation.**

*** 81. Is sufficient information readily available about the case?**

Yes

No

I'm not sure

*** 82. Do you have existing contact with the case owners? (e.g. in case you already worked with them in a different project, you know them through professional networks, etc.)**

Yes

No

*** 83. Please list the references you used for filling in this mapping questionnaire, including websites, articles, reports, etc.**

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EnergyPROSPECTS - Energy Citizenship (ENCI) Mapping tool

Picture (for online database and publications)

84. Please share at least 1 picture representing the case.

Choose File

Choose File

No file chosen

**85. If you have more pictures to share, you can upload one more here:
And please share the rest in this Google folder: <https://bit.ly/3diZXLX>**

Choose File

Choose File

No file chosen

86. What is the source of the picture(or pictures if you shared more)? Please include the link(s) or name(s) of source(s).

87. Have you already obtained permission to use the picture(s)? (We need to obtain permission to use pictures in our materials, so if you do not yet have the permission, you will need to obtain it.)

- It is my own picture (in this case we do not need additional permission :))
- It is a publicly available picture (e.g. on a website, in this case we do not need permission, but need to provide the source)
- Yes
- No
- Other, please explain:

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EnergyPROSPECTS - Energy Citizenship (ENCI) Mapping tool

Closing

Thank you for completing the survey for this case! :)

88. Please leave any additional comments you may have about the survey, the case, or anything related to your experience that may be useful for further work and analysis. E.g. have there been places in the survey where you have found it particularly hard to respond? or something that you particularly liked about your experience?

89. If you wish to receive a copy of your filled in survey about this case, please indicate here.

Yes, I would like to receive a copy of my filled in survey

No, I'm fine.